

Asset Based Risk Analysis: A Quantitative Approach for Libraries

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Abstract –

The information intensive functions of libraries are major force behind the increasing application of ICT for the effective organization and service. The range of vulnerabilities and threats involves in IT environments which need to be properly estimated in order to smooth functioning of the system. Information Security Management program is about management of risk, which is accomplished by developing a risk management and mitigation strategy, whereby assets, threats, and vulnerabilities are identified and the commensurate risk is quantified. Compare to qualitative risk analysis, quantitative risk analysis is easy to perform as calculating the potential lost in term of monetary value is not always possible for qualitative risk analysis. The success of quantitative risk analysis operation is heavily depends on application proper risk treatment and controls.

Keywords – Information Risk Analysis, Asset-based risk analysis, Information security Risk Management.

Introduction

The importance of information in today's society has led the scholars and leaders to claim the era of information which is shaping the concept of information society, a concept where information dominates new modes of social organization. Effective application of modern enabling technology for efficient handling and mobilization of timely information is the key feature of this developing information society. ICT has provided the powerful tools and platform for information handling as a new media of rapid communication and information exchange.

A strong connection exists in society between growing reliance on electronic Information System and associated technology, which has made information sharing, scholarly communication easier and less expensive. The increasing application of computer and

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telecommunication technology have evolved the global information society and stimulated the growth of an information industry within the private, government as well as academic sectors today. A columnist John MacColl (2010) argue that the economic potential of highly valued research is now evident as national economies shift to a dependence of knowledge and knowledge-based skills. Public funded universities are being drawn into national economic agendas in ways that are new to them and that challenge many traditional academic values (MacColl, John; 2010). The implication of this process is now resounds from all section and segment of our modern society including higher education. As a leader of the change the libraries of higher education are also responding with new role and responsibilities accordingly. The libraries are always been a place where informational and social infrastructures intersect within a physical infrastructure. Libraries are assumed to be a host of ever-changing social and symbolic functions and expected to symbolize the eminence of state, to integrally link ‘knowledge’ and ‘power’ – and more recently to serve as “community centres” or “public square.” (Mattern, Shannon, 2014).

Networked information collections in the libraries, allow online access to all type of documents and information including full-text and multimedia contents. The modern libraries are increasingly rely on various data storage technologies and process to widespread use of interoperable devices and development of a National Information System infrastructure and have integrated networked information resources of all kinds of new collaborative environments. The rise of digitization and digital library has become the ultimate appearance of modern library today. The digital environment has radically changed the way researcher find articles as well as the access and retrieval of it. The application of various sophisticated software to manage the services and electronic collection has become the inevitable need beside the increasing use of online reference sources, multimedia documents, digital objects, online databases etc, sometime such documents are outnumbered the print document in the libraries. Hence libraries are now passing through the transition phase which is being termed as “Hybrid Libraries”. The libraries are now furnished with several IT equipments; tools and technological intensive gadgets in order cope with diversified information need of their patrons and started spending significant amount of their shrinking budget over IT based business.

Unlike other social organizations, libraries are increasingly acknowledging the importance of information technology and have adopted embraced information system and technologies in

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order to survive in a competitive environment. Technological developments and the availability of online information resources have welcomed the benefits by users and librarians both. The role and the function of libraries in a technological driven world has greatly altered the existing system especially in term of library management, organization, acquisition, functions and services. With the advent of the information era, the rise of digitization and digital library has become the ultimate appearance of modern library today. The digital environment has radically changed the way researcher find articles as well as how they access and retrieve it. Libraries realize the storage of huge capacity and magnanimity information processing and make library users to get huge information resources. The digital library is in essence a multimedia information online repository takes distributed massive groups of information databases as resources, takes the network as transmission platform, and over comes the space and time limitation (Hui-Feng Shih and Chang-Tsun Li.)

However it involves severe risk and threats in addition to the great advantages such as hackers and computer virus. The anonymity of electronic world; pose the range of threats to global information society has made the situation worst ever before. Today greater importance is attached to intellectual property rights, which can lead to the embarrassment huge losses if part of secret information is lost. There can be serious abuse in the privacy of information. Moreover, the integrity of the systems could be compromised in term of confidentiality, availability and integrity of the whole library and information system.

Threats and Vulnerabilities

Security threat can be defined as every event that can result with information confidentiality, integrity and availability breaches, or with any other form of information system resources damage. In other words, it is a possible event that can harm an information system, where vulnerability is the degree of exposure in view of threat and the countermeasure is a set of actions implemented to prevent threats. In the domain of information system security different types of security threats classifications are used. The reason why threats classifications are necessary comes from the fact that if information systems resources should be protected one have to know the sources and the threats from which they are coming from. (BS 7799-2:2002). The vulnerability has defined by NIST SP 800-30 as it pertains to information systems – “A flaw or weakness in system security procedures, design, implementation, or internal controls that could be exercised (accidentally triggered or

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intentionally exploited) and result in a security breach or a violation of the system's security policy. Notice that the vulnerability can be a flaw or weakness in any aspect of the system." Vulnerabilities are not merely flaws in the technical protections provided by the system. Significant vulnerabilities are often contained in the standard operating procedures that systems administrators perform, the process that the help desk uses to reset passwords or inadequate log review.

Threats Source

Threat-Source is either intended and method targeted at the intentional exploitation of vulnerability or a situation and method that may accidentally trigger vulnerability. The threat is merely the potential for the exercise of a particular vulnerability. Threats in themselves are not actions. Threats must be coupled with threat-sources to become dangerous. This is an important distinction when assessing and managing risks, since each threat-source may be associated with a different likelihood, which, as will be demonstrated, affects risk assessment and risk management. It is often expedient to incorporate threat sources into threats.

1. **Human error:** Unintentional and careless handling by the users or operators of the system can cause inadvertent disclosure of confidential information.
2. **Computer abuse or crime:** The intended and malicious attack to steal information from sites. An Internet-based computer fraud can happen when a victim is expecting a large payoff for helping to move million of dollars out of a foreign country. 'Wire-fraud' is a specific form of computer-related crime where the means of communications is a central feature of the offence, credit card data from hacked websites, password-sniffing programs used to obtain information required to gain access to the password owner's system.
3. **Natural and political disasters:** The natural calamities and war, riots as well government policies can also undermine the whole information system seriously.
4. **Failure and incompatibility of hardware or software:** In the age of fastest growing technology, the incompatibility of software and hardware is a usual problem leads very serious issue in the desire and timely information exchange. The technical failures such as wrong and inadequate configuration, source code mismatch, become difficult to sort out the related problems and can put-down the entire system.

Risk Assessment

Risk is the potential harm that may arise from some current process or from some future event. IT security risk is the harm to a process or the related information resulting from some purposeful or accidental event that negatively impacts the process or the related information. The main aim of managing risk in an organization is to protect the integrity and assets of the organization. Therefore, risk management is a management function rather than a technical function.

Security Threat and Risk Assessments form a part of the risk management process to ensure responsible management and security of information system and resources. IT security places escalating demands on IT organization. Indeed, managing an institution's IT security risk through technical preparedness, policy and regulatory issues, and heightened awareness can add staffing and financial burdens to overtaxed organizations managing daily operations. One tool at hand is a risk assessment, "which assigns relative priorities for (IT security) mitigation plans and implementation" (EDUCASE/ Internet2 computer and network security task force risk assessment working group, 2006). The Security Threat and Risk Assessment is a structured method for gathering threat profile information. The objective of conducting a Security Threat and Risk Assessment is to determine the adequacy of current safeguards from the point of view of requirements, efficiency and cost. Risk Assessment must be conducted on all information systems. Risk is assessed by identifying threats and vulnerabilities, then determining the likelihood and impact for each risk.

Risk Treatment and application of controls

Risk treatment refers to identify the range of options for treating risk, assessing those options, preparing risk treatment plans and implementing them. It involves a process to modify a risk by changing the consequences that could occur or their likelihood. Several controls at various levels also expected to be applied in order to reduce adverse impact of certain threats. Controls mitigate risks identified in the Security Risk Assessment. The selection of controls is predicated on availability of assets and management's ability to accept certain risks in lieu of implementing controls. This can be prioritized by the risk value identified as according to the risk assessment program. (Conklin et al. 2005)

The options available for the treatment of risks include:

- Retain/accept the risk - if, after controls are put in place, the remaining risk is deemed acceptable to the organisation, the risk can be retained. However, plans should be put in place to manage/fund the consequences of the risk should it occur.
- Reduce the Likelihood of the risk occurring - by preventative maintenance, audit & compliance programs, supervision, contract conditions, policies & procedures, testing, investment & portfolio management, training of staff, technical controls and quality assurance programs etc.
- Reduce the Consequences of the risk occurring - through contingency planning, contract conditions, disaster recovery & business continuity plans, off-site back-up, public relations, emergency procedures and staff training etc.
- Transfer the risk - this involves another party bearing or sharing some part of the risk by the use of contracts, insurance, outsourcing, joint ventures or partnerships etc.
- Avoid the risk - decide not to proceed with the activity likely to generate the risk, where this is practicable.

Quantitative Asset- Based Risk Analysis

There are two approaches to risk assessment viz. quantitative risk analysis and qualitative risk analysis based on inverse impact of risk on the system. Qualitative risk assessment do not assign cost the elements of loss. It is more of consequent oriented approach. The seriousness of threats and the relative sensitivity of the assets are ranked or qualitative grading is provided for the qualitative assessment of the risk. On the other hand Quantitative risk analysis is done by assigning independently objective numeric values in monetary terms to the components of the risk assessment and to the assessment of potential losses. All the elements of this risk analysis such as asset value, impact, threat frequency, effectiveness, and costs of countermeasures are measured, rated and objective values are assigned. Although, 100% quantitative risk analysis is not possible in terms of practicability of a library activity, but still compare to qualitative it is rather more easy and effective method of risk analysis.

Quantitative risk assessment draws upon methodologies used by financial institutions and insurance companies. By assigning values to information, systems, business processes, recovery costs, etc., impact, and therefore risk, can be measured in terms of direct and indirect costs. Mathematically, quantitative risk can be expressed as Annualized Loss Expectancy (ALE). ALE is the expected monetary loss that can be expected for an asset due to a risk being realized over a one-year period.

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$$\text{ALE} = \text{SLE} \times \text{ARO}$$

Where:

- SLE (Single Loss Expectancy) is the value of a single loss of the asset. This may or may not be the entire asset. This is the impact of the loss.
- ARO (Annualized Rate of Occurrence) is how often the loss occurs. This is the likelihood.

Mathematically, this gets complicated very quickly, involving statistical techniques that are beyond the scope of this discussion. While utilizing quantitative risk assessment seems straightforward and logical, there are issues with using this approach with information systems. While the cost of a system may be easy to define, the indirect costs, such as value of the information, lost production activity and the cost to recover is imperfectly known at best. Moreover, the other major element of risk, likelihood, is often even less perfectly known. (Elky, Steve. 2006).

Quantitative risk analysis is considered the best and most suitable method in asset-based risk assessment. Whereas asset-based risk assessments are still widely regarded as best practice, and present a robust methodology for conducting risk analysis. It is commonly believed that an asset-based information security risk assessment provides a thorough and comprehensive approach to conducting a risk assessment.

The Steps of Asset-based Risk Analysis

In order to conduct a comprehensive risk analysis a systematic method needs to be employed which can explain in following steps.

1. Understanding the importance of assets for asset owner –

The ‘asset owner’ is an individual or entity that has responsibility for controlling the production, development, maintenance, use and security of an information asset. The critical function and business of an asset owner have different importance of every asset.

2. Identification of asset –

Through a series of interview with asset owner a comprehensive list of asset can be prepared for further analysis.

3. Identification of potential threats and vulnerabilities-

Once the asset register has been compiled, the next step is to identify any potential threats and vulnerabilities that could pose risks to those assets. A vulnerability /

weakness of an asset or control can be defined as one that can be exploited by one or more threats.

4. Determination of Risk Acceptable Value (RAV) -

Many assets having inbuilt vulnerability and prone to be threat intensive in such case the risk become unavoidable, hence with the consent of asset owners the potential risk acceptance value needs to determine.

5. Assigning the value –

A scale with weight of value requires developing in order to assign the numbers to risk and its possible impact in terms of confidentiality, integrity, availability of system and probability of occurrence based on frequency.

6. Calculation of Risk Priority Number (RPN) –

Based on the given value to each risk in terms of confidentiality, integrity, availability and probability a risk priority numbers can determine which ideally should be less than the risk acceptable value. If it is more than this then necessary control need to be applied until it comes below than the RAV this process known as risk treatment.

The above method we will try to understand by an illustrative example of library. The modern libraries are able perform their information intensive functions and services with the help of modern technology. The libraries are equipped with the range of technological assets of crucial importance for business continuity purpose, such as personnel computers, server, software, data and databases, network, RFID, router- switches, CCTV, etc. Each of these equipments used for different functions with the inbuilt limitations and potential to certain vulnerabilities and expose to its various threats and risk. The Improper handling or error can cost catastrophic impact on the system's confidentiality, integrity, and availability. For instance a server of a library holds very crucial information adhere to entire functions and business of a library. It holds all backup files and sql and exe. files of the library management software. The server is vulnerable to corrupt, tempered, damage, hacking etc from the range of threats source. As a result data may corrupt or loss and the whole system may down to collapse.

The value with weight of 1 to 6 as a impact of occurrence such as –

High (H) = 6; Medium (M) = 4 and Low (L) = 2.

At the same time we will have to determine the Risk Acceptable Value (RAV) with consent of asset owner say for example $RAV = 70$. The exercise need to be repeated by applying risk treatment in terms of controls until the RAV doesn't comes below the RAV. This can be represented in the tabular form by assigning the value from 1 to 6 of risk impact in the cost of Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability and Probability.

			Risk Impact				
Asset	Vulnerability	Threat	Confidentiality (C)	Integrity (I)	Availability (A)	Probable	RPN
Server	Corrupt Data	System Down	2	6	6	4	$2 \times 6 \times 6 \times 4 = 288$

The Risk Probability Numbers (RPN) is more than the value of Risk Acceptable Value (RAV) i.e. 70 that we determined hence it requires the rigorous risk treatment with some controls to be applied.

1st Risk Treatment – Having more mirror server at different location with proper physical security.

			Risk Impact				
Asset	Vulnerability	Threat	Confidentiality (C)	Integrity (I)	Availability (A)	Probable	RPN
Server	Corrupt Data	System Down	2	4	2	4	$2 \times 4 \times 2 \times 4 = 64$

The process of applying risk treatment and controls needs to repeat until the value of RPN doesn't comes below the RAV. Here in this case, now the value of RPN is less than RAV (70), one can go on apply more risk treatment but there cannot be zero (0) risk impact hence RPN never be zero.

Discussion

Risk management is the process that allows managers to balance the operational and economic costs of protective measures and achieve gains in mission capability by protecting the IT systems and data that support their organizations' missions. This process is not unique to the IT environment; indeed it pervades decision-making in all areas of our daily lives.

(Gary Stoneburner, Alice Goguen, and Alexis Feringa. 2002). The asset based quantitative risk analysis is easy to perform as assets are easy to estimate for the understanding of possible vulnerabilities and threats. The asset owner can also involve in the process which helps in comprehensive risk analysis. The analysis is certainly helpful for identification of risk owner and threat source for further effective management of libraries. The logical application of various controls and security practice give librarians an opportunity to have insight about the current information security practices in the library. The information security standard doesn't speak much about how to apply of controls? But, rather suggest the policy to be framed and insisting on its complain, from this point of view the risk assessment is also become a prime function of any information security programme.

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